

1 **Validation of an analytical method to determine melatonin and compounds related to L-**
2 **Tryptophan metabolism using UHPLC/HRMS**

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13 **Keywords:** indolic compounds, wine, yeast, *Saccharomyces*, synthetic must, exact mass.

14 **Abstract**

15 Melatonin is a bioactive compound that is present in wines because of the metabolism of L-
16 Tryptophan by yeasts. Even though the complete pathway of synthesis is not well elucidated,
17 certain related indolic compounds might be involved in it. Consequently, their determination is a
18 matter of interest. On one hand, their formation during fermentation might be related to a specific
19 role for yeast's metabolism, not known so far. On the other hand, the synthesis by yeasts of
20 bioactive compounds with putative health benefits for consumers, such as melatonin or serotonin,
21 is a relevant matter.

22 This paper aims to develop and validate an analytical method by UHPLC/HRMS to monitor both
23 melatonin and related indolic compounds, in order to decrease their detection limits and make it
24 possible to assess their occurrence in culture medium and fermented products. In addition, the
25 other objective is to evaluate the production of these compounds by a commercial *Saccharomyces*
26 *cerevisiae* used to make white wines.

27 Diminishing the limit of detection below 0.5 ng mL^{-1} for all compounds under study is an
28 achievement of this work. Furthermore, the strain under study (AROMA WHITE) has been found
29 to synthesize melatonin and related compounds as serotonin. Additionally, the evolution of these
30 compounds over time may contribute to understanding the role they play in yeast metabolism.

31 **Introduction**

32 Melatonin (MEL) has previously been evidenced in wines (Mercolini et al. 2008; Stege et al.
33 2010; Rodriguez-Naranjo et al. 2011; Mercolini et al. 2012; Vitalini et al. 2013; Vigentini et al.
34 2015). Despite it having been detected in wine after fermentation, revealing the role of
35 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, little is known beyond this; specifically, its formation by yeasts under
36 fermentation conditions needs to be unravelled. Nevertheless, L-tryptophan (L-TRP) has been
37 pinpointed as its precursor (Sprenger et al. 1999; Murch et al. 2000). Additionally, serotonin
38 (SERO), which happens to be an intermediary in the MEL pathway in plants (Iriti 2009; Feng et
39 al. 2014), has been reported in wines (Manfroi et al. 2009; Wang et al. 2014). On the other hand,
40 literature on the chemical composition of wines describes that some of these indolic compounds,
41 such as Tryptophol (TOL) and 3-indolylacetic acid (3-IAA), are present in wines (Mattivi et al.
42 1999; Maslov et al. 2011; Favre et al. 2014) being the latest an off-flavour.

43 Other analytical techniques to determine L-TRP and derivative compounds in wines have been
44 previously used (Garcia-Parrilla et al. 2009). It is worth mentioning the ELISA assay, since it was
45 used to identify MEL in serum (Welp et al. 2010). However, ELISA results were reported to be
46 inaccurate for wine analysis due to matrix effects (Rodriguez-Naranjo et al. 2011). Indeed, the
47 presence of a substance with a similar structure in wines could cause interference.

48 Originally, HPLC coupled with fluorescence detectors was used (Mattivi et al. 1999; Mercolini
49 et al. 2008), but this technique is not suitable for unequivocal identification and therefore mass
50 spectrometry techniques were preferred (Kocadağlı et al. 2014). At present, hybrid quadrupole-
51 orbitrap offers a more accurate analysis of compounds based on the use of exact mass. Therefore,
52 the optimization of an analytical method based on high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS)
53 techniques is required to achieve lower limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ)
54 values, in addition to the subsequent validation of analytical parameters.

55 In order to gain more knowledge about L-TRP derivatives formation, a simultaneous analysis is
56 necessary. The pathway in *Saccharomyces* has not been established yet. In animals and plants
57 (Figure 1), the precursor is L-TRP, which is hydroxylated to form 5-hydroxytryptophan (5-
58 HTRP). A decarboxylase transforms 5-HTRP into SERO and then into N-acetylserotonin
59 (NACSERO). The last step in this pathway consists of MEL formation, through the action of a
60 methyl transferase (Harumi and Matsushima 2000; Iriti and Varoni 2015). Plants also have an
61 alternative pathway to synthesize MEL from L-TRP. A decarboxylase transforms it into
62 Tryptamine (TRYPT) and then it is hydroxylated to SERO. The rest of the pathway is similar to
63 animals (Tan et al. 2014).

64 Other compounds, such as TRYPT, 3-IAA and TOL are included in other pathways. In particular,
65 TRYPT requires only one step to its formation, via L-TRP decarboxylase. Indeed, the literature

66 reports these compounds in wines (Mattivi et al. 1999; Maslov et al. 2011; Rodriguez-Naranjo et
67 al. 2013; Piasta et al. 2014; Žulj et al. 2015). On the other hand, L-Tryptophan ethyl ester (L-TRP
68 EE), which has been recently reported to occur during alcoholic fermentation of must (Vigentini
69 et al. 2015), presents the same exact mass as MEL. Due to a misinterpretation of the data, it was
70 previously taken as a MEL isomer, but Iriti *et al.* elucidated its structure (Gardana et al. 2014).
71 This compound is formed via esterification, although whether all *S.cerevisiae* strains are able to
72 synthesize it is not clear, neither is the role it plays.

73 The aim of this work is to develop and validate an analytical method by Ultra High Performance
74 Liquid Chromatography coupled to High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC/HRMS)
75 techniques to simultaneously identify and quantify analytes related to L-TRP metabolism, in order
76 to gain knowledge of yeast metabolism. To this end, optimization to achieve a low LOD is
77 required, as MEL is in very low concentration and the same is expected for compounds involved
78 in the pathway.

79

80 **Materials and methods**

81

82 Synthetic must

83 Synthetic must (SM) was prepared following the Riou *et al.* method (Riou et al. 1997), with a
84 slight modification in sugar (100 g L⁻¹ fructose and 100 g L⁻¹ glucose) and organic acid content
85 (tartaric acid 3 g L⁻¹, citric acid 0.3 g L⁻¹ and malic acid 5 g L⁻¹). The other compounds were
86 maintained without modifications: amino acids (purity ≥ 99%); mineral salts (KH₂PO₄ 0.75 g L⁻¹,
87 K₂SO₄ 0.5 g L⁻¹, MgSO₄·7H₂O 0.250 g L⁻¹, CaCl₂ 0.155 g L⁻¹, NaCl 0.200 g L⁻¹, NH₄Cl 0.460
88 g L⁻¹, MnSO₄·H₂O 4 g L⁻¹, ZnSO₄·H₂O 4 g L⁻¹, CuSO₄·5H₂O 1 g L⁻¹, KI 1g L⁻¹, CoCl₂·6H₂O 0.4
89 g L⁻¹, H₃BO₃ 1 g L⁻¹ and (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄ 1 g L⁻¹); vitamins (myo-inositol 2 g L⁻¹, calcium
90 pantothenate 0.150 g L⁻¹, thiamine hydrochloride 0.025 g L⁻¹, nicotinic acid 0.200 g L⁻¹,
91 pyridoxine 0.025 g L⁻¹ and biotine 0,0003 g L⁻¹); anaerobic factors (ergosterol 1.5 g 100 mL⁻¹,
92 oleic acid 0.5 g 100 mL⁻¹ and Tween 80 0.5 ml L⁻¹). All reagents were purchased from Sigma
93 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

94 L-TRP (cell culture grade) was supplied by Panreac (Darmstadt, Germany); standards of 5-HTRP,
95 SERO (purity ≥ 98 %), NACSERO (TLC, purity ≥ 98 %), MEL (TLC, purity ≥ 98 %), TRYPT
96 (analytical standard), TOL (purity 97 %), 3-IAA (T, purity > 98%) and L-TRP EE (AT, purity ≥
97 99 %) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Formic acid was provided by
98 Prolabo® (Obregón, México) and methanol for liquid chromatography was supplied by Merck
99 (Darmstadt, Germany).

100 Yeast strain

101 A commercial strain of wine yeast was tested under fermentation conditions in SM. A *S.cerevisiae*
102 strain, currently selected for white wine making, was used (AROMA WHITE). It was purchased
103 from Enartis (Trecate (NO), Italy). The yeast was rehydrated in a bath at 37 °C for 30 minutes,
104 following the manufacturer's instructions. Then, it was plated on yeast extract peptone dextrose
105 (YPD) agar and incubated at 28 °C for 48 hours. The pre-inoculum was prepared in 150 mL of
106 YPD broth and left for 24 hours under stirring (150 rpm) at 28° C, before inoculation in SM.

107

108 SM inoculation

109 SM was performed in 10 L of distilled water. Firstly, the amounts of sugars, acids and salts
110 described above were added. The resulting solution was stirred to homogenize the medium and
111 the pH was adjusted to 3.45 with NaOH. Subsequently, SM was autoclaved at 121 °C for 21
112 minutes. Then, amino acids, trace elements, vitamins and anaerobic factors were added
113 aseptically. This step prevents the degradation of thermolabile compounds due to the high
114 temperatures reached during the sterilization process. Finally, just before inoculation, the SM was
115 distributed in sterile Erlenmeyer flask of 1 L capacity with 750 mL each. To end, they were
116 inoculated with 10⁵ cells mL⁻¹. Each flask was capped with plugs with two gaps to maintain
117 sterility. A Pasteur pipette was used in one gap to allow the egress of carbon dioxide, while the
118 other one was reserved for sampling. Fermentation was carried out in triplicate.

119

120 Sampling

121 Sampling was performed daily for 9 days, taking 10 mL from each flask. Subsequently, their
122 contents were divided into 2 aliquots: a 1 mL aliquot was diluted (1:100) for cell counting in a
123 Neubauer chamber as a duplicate; the other 9 mL aliquot was centrifuged at 4,500 rpm for 3
124 minutes at room temperature. Following this, 2 mL of supernatant were taken, to measure the
125 residual sugars in the medium, while the rest was stored at -20 ° C until analysis. Fermentations
126 were considered to have finished when the residual sugars in the medium were below 2 g L⁻¹.

127

128 Sample preparation

129 Prior to UHPLC/HRMS analysis, sample compounds were extracted as previously described by
130 Rodriguez-Naranjo *et al.* (Rodriguez-Naranjo et al. 2011). Briefly, C18 SPE cartridges (Variant,
131 Agilent) were conditioned with 2 mL of methanol and 2 mL of milliQ water. Then, 500 µL of
132 sample were loaded. Cartridges were washed with a 10% v/v methanol/water solution. Finally,

133 analytes were eluted with 1 mL of methanol. Extracts were filtered (13 mm VWR Syringe Filter,
134 0.45 μm PTFE) to remove impurities before analysis.

135

136 UHPLC parameters

137 The analysis was carried out in an UHPLC Dionex Ultimate 3000 system (ThermoScientific, San
138 Jose, USA) consisting of an RS Pump (HPG-3400RS), an RS Column Compartment (TCC-
139 3000RS) and an RS Autosampler (WPS-3000RS). All devices were controlled by Chromeleon
140 Express Software. The column used for the analysis was a ZORBAX RRHD SB-C18 (2.1 x 100
141 mm, 1.8 μm particle size) with a guard column (2.1 x 5 mm, 1.8 μm particle size). Both of them
142 were purchased from Agilent Technologies (Waldbronn, Germany). The analysis temperature
143 was set at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

144 The chromatographic conditions consisted of two mobile phases, water (A) and methanol (B),
145 both with 0.1% formic acid, with a gradient elution programmed as follows: 95% A, 5% B (0-2
146 min); 0% A, 100% B (2-13 min); 95% A, 5 % B (13.1-15 min). The flow selected was 0.5 mL
147 min^{-1} and the injection volume was 5 μL .

148

149 HRMS parameters

150 A Thermo Scientific QexactiveTM hybrid quadrupole-orbitrap mass spectrometer (Bremen,
151 Germany) was used coupled to the UHPLC system described earlier. Compound ionization was
152 performed through a heated electrospray ionization source (HESI) in positive mode. The
153 following parameters were optimized to carry out the analysis: heater temperature was set at 440
154 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and capillary temperature at 270 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; spray voltage was optimized at 3.5 kV; the flow rates of
155 sheath gas, auxiliary gas and sweep gas were established at 53, 14 and 3 arbitrary units,
156 respectively. Once a week, the Qexactive was calibrated according to the manufacturer's
157 instructions for good practice.

158 A target-MS² mode was set to perform the analysis. The molecular formula and exact mass of
159 each compound were acquired from *PubChem* and *ChemSpider* public databases. A mix of 9
160 standards at 3-55 ng mL^{-1} was infused into the system with a syringe at a low flow rate (3 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$)
161 ¹⁾ in order to obtain the main fragments of every compound. A target experiment using eight
162 entries was used, since MEL and L-TRP EE possess the same exact mass. The acquisition of
163 every compound had a specific start-and end-time range. SERO and 5-HTRP were analysed from
164 0.50 to 2 min; L-TRP and TRYPT from 3.60 to 4.60 min; NACSERO from 5 to 5.70 min; MEL
165 and L-TRP EE from 6.10 to 7.60; and finally, TOL and 3-IAA from 6.60 to 7.60 min. The

166 normalized collision energy used (NCE) was 20. In this mode, HRMS analysis had an RP of
167 35,000 FWHM, with an isolation window of 1.0 m/z and S-lens RF level of 50 %. For a maximum
168 injection time (IT) of 100 ms, the automatic gain control (AGC) target analysed 1×10^6 ions.
169 Xcalibur Software (version 3.0.63) and TraceFinder™ Software (version 3.1) (Thermo Fisher
170 Scientific, Waltham, MA) were used for the subsequent data analysis.

171

172 Method validation

173 This analytical method was validated following AOAC instructions (AOAC 2012). Linearity,
174 LOD, LOQ, within-lab reproducibility and repeatability were the parameters analysed. For
175 linearity, 10-point calibration curves were used in a range of 2300-0.01 ng mL⁻¹ in triplicate for
176 all compounds. LOD and LOQ were calculated through the calibration graph slope and its residual
177 standard deviation. For LOD, a factor of 3.3 was used to calculate the value. On the other hand,
178 LOQ was obtained by using a factor of 10.

179 A set of three samples spiked with different concentrations (50, 25 and 5 ng mL⁻¹) were employed
180 to determine within-lab reproducibility and repeatability. The former was evaluated with a daily
181 analysis of each spiked sample over 5 days. Repeatability was assessed in a single day-long work
182 session, with 5 replicates of each concentration.

183 Statistical analysis

184 Differences between the indolic compounds during fermentation by *S.cerevisiae* AROMA
185 WHITE were determined with one-way ANOVA analysis by the Statistica Software (StaSoft Inc
186 2005). The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

187

188 **Results and discussion**

189

190 UHPLC/HRMS method optimization

191 An analytical method by UHPLC/HRMS was optimized to determine L-TRP and derivative
192 compounds. Figure 2 shows the chromatographic peaks obtained for each compound. A run time
193 of less than 8 minutes was achieved. Good resolution was observed in the analysis due to the
194 sensitivity of the Qexactive. The order of elution was as follows: SERO and 5-HTRP appeared
195 first, with a retention time (R_T) of less than 2 minutes; subsequently, L-TRP and TRYPT eluted
196 after 4 minutes. Even though there was a significant time space between the first two analytes and
197 the following ones, the most suitable peak resolution was achieved this way. NACSERO had an

198 R_T of 5.24 minutes, whereas L-TRP EE was eluted at 6.63 minutes. The rest of the compounds
199 (TOL, 3-IAA, MEL) were obtained at an R_T of between 7.09 and 7.14 minutes. Exact mass
200 allowed each peak to be identified, even though the R_T differs within just a few seconds. Table 1
201 displays the R_T , accurate mass of main fragment $[M+H]^+$, relative intensities found, chemical
202 formula and calculated error (ppm) for the compounds included in this study. Error was below 3
203 ppm in all cases. SERO, TRYPT, 3-IAA acid and TOL had only one main fragment. SERO
204 fragmentation m/z 160.07544 was the result of the loss of an amine group. This fact was common
205 to most of the compounds, since its bond with the indolic ring was quite weak, as in the case of
206 TRYPT (m/z 144.08038). TOL presented dehydroxylation of the hydroxyl group (m/z
207 144.08053). 3-IAA obtained its main fragment m/z 130.06501 after the loss of the carboxyl group
208 in the lateral chain. These functional groups were putatively the weakest, so they were easily
209 breakable during the analysis. The 5-HTRP showed a main fragment m/z 204.06520 that was also
210 due to a deamination. However, it also presented another fragment (m/z 162.05480), whose
211 formation is not yet clear, but which was useful to identify the compound. NACSERO had the
212 same identification fragment as SERO (m/z 160.07542). MEL and L-TRP EE shared a molecular
213 formula and exact mass. Iriti *et al.* (Gardana et al. 2014) has previously described the pattern of
214 fragmentation of each compound. Even though they had similar fragmentations determined with
215 a QTRAP (m/z 233 \rightarrow m/z 174 and m/z 233 \rightarrow m/z 216), their different R_T and fragment intensities
216 allowed them to be identified without any misinterpretation of the data obtained.

217

218 Method validation

219 Table 2 shows the validation parameters of the analytical method, including linearity, LOD, LOQ,
220 within-lab reproducibility and repeatability for the 9 compounds analysed.

221 Linearity values were calculated through the correlation coefficient (R^2) of the curves obtained
222 for each compound within the expected range of concentrations. All the values had an R^2 between
223 0.998-1.000, showing quite good linearity. The repeatability values obtained for all compounds
224 were below 2% with the exception of SERO which highest value was near 21 % but within the
225 AOAC recommendations. On the other hand, reproducibility reached values between 4 and 26 %.
226 The AOAC recommends a reproducibility of 45-32 % for the low limit (5 ng mL⁻¹) and 32-16 %
227 for the other concentrations analysed, so reproducibility was adequate.

228 Regarding LOD values, we could achieve to decrease MEL LOD to 0.0047 ng mL⁻¹. As far as
229 MEL is concerned, other authors have reported LOD values for MEL determined by HPLC-
230 MS/MS on different matrixes. Kocadağlı et al. analyzed MEL in red wine and obtained a LOD of
231 0.034 ng mL⁻¹ with a triple quadrupole (Kocadağlı et al. 2014). On the other hand, a LOD of 30.16
232 ng mL⁻¹ was reported in a study of MEL during all the steps of the winemaking (Gomez et al.

233 2012). Rodriguez-Naranjo et al obtained a LOD of and 0.13 ng mL^{-1} by using a ion-trap in the
234 study of MEL in wine (Rodriguez-Naranjo et al. 2011). Even though these values are quite low,
235 they are higher than the one achieved in this work. Thus, working with a hybrid quadrupole-
236 orbitrap mass spectrometer demonstrated a better election when it is necessary to low the LOD
237 values in order to improve the analysis.

238

239 Analysis of indolic compounds during fermentation in SM

240 In order to test the suitability of the method to monitor the evolution of L-TRP derivatives during
241 fermentation, an experiment with *S.cerevisiae* var. AROMA WHITE was performed. Figure 3
242 shows the evolution of cell density during alcoholic fermentation. Cell population underwent a
243 significant growth rate reaching the maximum at day 2. Then, it decreased quickly at day 3 and it
244 was remained constant until the end of alcoholic fermentation (day 7) in a SM. The indolic
245 compounds under study were monitored over this period. The results are shown in Table 3. It is
246 important to note that all of the compounds were determined at least once during the fermentation
247 experiment, except for NACSERO. The concentration of L-TRP, which is the precursor of the
248 pathway, decreased during fermentation, as expected. Yeasts need this amino acid to synthesize
249 the rest of the compounds. Gil-Agustí *et al.* (Gil-Agustí et al. 2007) analysed L-TRP content in
250 wines and found low concentrations ($0.20\text{-}1.98 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$). In contrast, levels in must of around
251 7000 ng mL^{-1} have been reported. Although its levels in the same wine after alcoholic and
252 malolactic fermentation were lower ($3,660 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ and $3.11 \times 10^6 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$, respectively) (Wang et
253 al. 2014) those values are higher than the ones obtained in this experiment. On the other hand, the
254 presence of 5-HTRP also decreased. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time it has been
255 determined in SM fermented with *S.cerevisiae*. At the beginning of fermentation, the highest
256 concentrations were quantified; these subsequently decreased during the process (19 to 3 ng mL^{-1}).
257 The initial amount of 5-HTRP that was observed in the SM is derived from the solution of
258 amino acids added before the fermentation process. Although yeasts did not synthesized this
259 compound they used it as a minority nitrogen source.

260 SERO increased during fermentation from less than 1 ng mL^{-1} to more than 4.5 ng mL^{-1} .
261 Nevertheless, concentrations 1,000 times higher have been assessed in wines (nearly 3000 ng mL^{-1})
262 following malolactic fermentation (Wang et al. 2014). The maximum concentration of MEL
263 was achieved at day 2, coinciding with Rodríguez-Naranjo *et al.* and Iriti et al. (Rodriguez-
264 Naranjo et al. 2011; Vigentini et al. 2015). It seems to be directly related with the cell growth at
265 day 2, when it also reached the maximum value. Then, MEL content also decreased until it
266 completely disappear at day 5. Other authors also detected MEL from day 2 but its concentration
267 remained constant during time (Gomez et al. 2012). TRYPT was also synthesized during

268 fermentation, but at lower levels (0.7 - 1.60 ng mL⁻¹) than have been reported before (Gil-Agustí
269 et al. 2007; Rodriguez-Naranjo et al. 2013). Even though yeasts played an important role in its
270 formation, the reached concentrations did not show this metabolite was a main one of the L-TRP
271 metabolism.

272 Furthermore, the concentration of 3-IAA increased sharply in day 1 up to 84 ng mL⁻¹ and then
273 decreased, especially between day 1 and day 3 to 3 ng mL⁻¹. Maslov *et al.* has found higher
274 concentrations in final wines (25-30 ng mL⁻¹) (Maslov et al. 2011). TOL concentration was the
275 highest of the analytes. On day 1, the concentration obtained was 14,000 ng mL⁻¹ and on day 3, it
276 increased up to 19,000 ng mL⁻¹. Nevertheless, its levels had decreased to 16,500 ng mL⁻¹ by day
277 7. Favre *et al.* found low quantities in Tannat wines (640-1,450 ng mL⁻¹), but the wine-making
278 procedure influenced this data (Favre et al. 2014). This metabolite appeared in the solution of
279 amino acids, so it was observed at day 0. The significant increase at day 1 brings to light that
280 yeasts synthesized it during fermentation process. Then, the decrease at the following days it was
281 likely caused by the conjugation of 3-IAA with other compounds, in order to protect the molecule
282 of the peroxidation (Sitbon et al. 1993; Hoenicke et al. 2001).

283 In relation to L-TRP EE, a continuous increase was noticed during fermentation: from 2.20 ng
284 mL⁻¹ on day 2, to 17.48 ng mL⁻¹ on day 7. Iriti *et al.* also reported concentrations of this compound
285 in the laboratory medium (Vigentini et al. 2015), but they found a tendency to decrease over time,
286 which could be attributed either to the different strain used or medium composition. Unlike the
287 SM used in this work, their medium composition consisted on buffered liquid mineral medium,
288 containing glucose and yeast nitrogen base (YNB) with 2 different concentrations of L-TRP (20
289 and 100 mg L⁻¹).

290 Yeasts use L-TRP and transform it into metabolites. Our data supports that 5-HTRP is used during
291 fermentation the first steps and then decreases afterwards, while the other intermediates start to
292 increase. Despite SERO being the precursor of MEL, it keeps increasing while MEL appears in a
293 very tiny quantity and finally disappears.

294

295 **Conclusions**

296 A validated method for the identification of derivative compounds of the L-TRP. metabolism was
297 developed successfully and LOD and LOQ were lowered with the use of a hybrid quadrupole-
298 orbitrap. It is clear that determined compounds (5-HTRP, SERO, MEL, 3-IAA, TRYPT, TOL, L-
299 TRP EE) are involved in *Saccharomyces* metabolism and this is a point of departure for further
300 studies, which are required to understand their role. In addition, 5-HTRP was identified in must

301 for the first time. Nevertheless, there is still a need to study yeast metabolism of L-TRP derivatives
302 in greater depth.

303

304 **Acknowledgements**

305 The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the Spanish Ministry of
306 Education, Culture and Sport (FPU13/04820). The authors would also like to thank Rocío
307 Valderrama for her technical support at HRMS central service.

308

309 **Compliance with Ethical Standards**

310 **Funding:** This work was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness
311 (AGL2013-47300-C3-3-R).

312 **Conflict of interest:** Edwin Fernández-Cruz, M.Antonia Álvarez-Fernández, Eva Valero, A.M.
313 Troncoso and M.C. García-Parrilla declare that they have no conflict of interest. This study does
314 not contain any studies with human or animal subjects.

315 **Ethical approval:** This article does not contain any studies with human participants performed
316 by any of the authors.

317 **Informed consent:** Not applicable.

318

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Figure captions

- 409 **Fig.1** Synthesis of compounds derived from L-Tryptophan in animals and plants
- 410 **Fig.2** Target MS² mode results with R_T and relative abundance of each indolic compound
- 411 **Fig.3** Evolution of cell population during 7 days of the fermentation process